

Contributions of Indian Prime Ministers to Social Welfare

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Abstract: Social Welfare has been embedded as a major spirit with the Indian constitutions, however, there are some Prime Ministers who used this constitutional provision to a great extent. They were able to take forward this notion and make some special arrangements. Therefore, this paper expedites some of the contributions of different Prime Ministers of India ensuring social welfare. Different prime ministers during the period 1947 up to 2015 were studied. If *Nehru* and some other prime ministers can be remembered for social welfare enactments, *Narendra Modi* could be remembered for implementing those provisions through good governance and administration.

Key words: Social Welfare in India; Prime Minister's Contribution; Welfare State in India

Aim and objectives:

This would be one of the major social scientific researches that investigated the roles and contribution towards *Social Welfare* at the levels of different Prime Ministers of India, starting from the first Prime Minister *Pandit Nehru* to the present Prime Minister *Dr. Manmohan Singh*. The research scholar and team would aim to conduct and present according to customs, traditions and practices of social science research.

Statement of the problem:

A Prime Minister has to contemplate the social problems, social needs and ready to take action for policy formulation. *In a welfare state, Social Welfare* is an arrangement to support and provide a *Social Security* cover to the society, family and its members in case certain urgent situation. *Social Security* transformed through the process of *Social Transformation* and *Social Change*. The society suffering from *Social Problems* causes *Social Needs*, and that accumulated *Social Needs* required intervention. That intervention comes differently in different forms of societies such as Agrarian, Industrial or Modern. The core principles of the *Modern Societies* usually based upon Democracy, Secularism, and the Welfare State. The customary laws remained prominent in agrarian societies since antiquities, however, democratic India now governed by Constitutional laws. Constitutional laws being supreme each form of society have to undergo a transformation to accept those constitutional laws which were so contrasting with respect to customary laws, however constitutional laws mostly prevailed yet customary traditions could not remain without creating impacts. In a democracy like India social welfare arrangement have to depend upon the policies as social policy would decide how and government would respond or not respond to a particular Social Need. The policy being important the role of a Prime Minister becomes important.

The contemporary Indian societies used to be a mixture of Agrarian, Industrial and Modern Societies. Such a mix up and tremendous diversity in sociology and physiology of the population demanded arrangements for Social Welfare based upon a vigorous appraisal of Social Needs at the level of a Prime Minister and his organs of administrations including institutes and organizations. In a surplus society either agrarian or industrial different Social Policies usually adopted, however deficient societies with products of agriculture and industry, it becomes so challenging for a

Prime Minister to act accordingly, plan and implement precisely.

The position, dossier and tradition of Prime Minister in India have been as momentous as head of the government the role of a Prime Minister has been so far modernizer. The speeches, deliberations, attitude, and taking a stand over *Social Welfare* issues become momentous for a Prime Minister. India becomes a welfare state had adopted policies for the welfare of people as state responsibilities. Policy initiatives required sanction by the Prime Minister. Therefore, every policy, programs in the country must reflect and guide through people friendly policies. The executive decisions of a Prime Minister used to be so crucial to lead the nation accordingly to set agenda by the intimates of the nations.

Indian *Social Welfare* arrangements were not symbolic, however, that was more systematic, logical and philosophical. In addition, *Social Welfare* in India appeared most scientific having great utilities in serving the interests of the target population. *Social Welfare* in India appeared based upon several fundamental principles such as democracy, socialism and secularism that so rare even in more modern and industrial societies of the developed countries. Even those fundamental principles adopted for the Social Welfare not get diluted by the time however that get strengthened from time to time and so much so that even post LPG or Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization of the Indian economy those principles never diluted and get strengthened. Even the NDA government could not dilute those principles. That's why we could see that in India programs like *Indira Awas Yojna*, *Jawahar Rojgar Yojna*, *Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan*, *National Rural Health Mission*, *Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Abhiyan* all became the backbone of the Social Welfare in India. Hardly any country in the world could be able to do so. Job reservation for weaker section, seat reservation in democratic institutions for weaker sections and women, schemes for minorities and schedule castes and tribes could not be done without a firm foundation laid in this country quite early. Even the private sector made to work towards their social responsibilities. Subsidies for farmers, industries, especially cottage industries have not subsided. Scholarships and educational assistances to poor students got never sidelined. Mahatma Gandhi views about *Gram Swarajya* and *Swadeshi* maintained at the same time care also taken to make this country progress in science and technology so that

it truly became an agrarian-modern-industrial societies. The welfare of the industrial working class, agrarian, working class and professional working class was more scientific, systematic and institutionalized, which could not find in any other country of the world. Setting up and strengthening *Punchatati Raj Institutions*, functioning in democratic manner would be the single example in this world.

A Prime Minister's idea about democracy, socialism used to be so relevant and respected. A Prime Minister takes strong line towards principles of democracy, secularism and socialism as head of the government usually so good for people. A Prime Minister's idea about *democracy*, socialism, and *secularism* required appraisal and considered in respective terms with some patriots such as *Churchill*, *Roosevelt*, *Chiang Kai-shank* and even *Gandhi* (Walsh, 1940). The relevance of a Prime Minister remained undiminished and in fact, his ideas and approach to political, economic and social issues are more relevant (Chittaranjan, 1973).

Nehru wanted to combine democracy with socialism, however he wanted socialism to come through peaceful means (Mahashwetadevi, 1990). The Planning Commission constituted by him and he choosing mixed economy was driven from his socialist principles (Shiya, 2012). *Nehru* had dreamt about an Indian society truly agrarian and industrial however, based upon modern principles of democracy, socialism and secularism. Further, he laid great stress on scientific and spiritual principles. Towards strengthening democracy, secularism and socialism *Nehru* made no compromise and he went upon to dismantle all feudal and religious hard beliefs and institutions. He always wanted to keep the country away from conflicts and war and chose non-alignment as a part of his formidable foreign policy however, he never distanced from developing countries. *Nehru* was so correct in his assertion "*We talk about a welfare state and direct our energies towards its realization. The welfare must be a common property of everyone in India and not the monopoly of a privileged group, as it is today, in particular those who are underprivileged today and have no opportunities of growth and progress that must be brought within its field*" (Commission, 1951). *Nehru* wanted the welfare state must ensure minimum opportunities for the physical and social wellbeing of its citizens. He emphasized *Social Welfare* necessary to address the issue of poverty, unemployment and disparities. Most importantly, *Nehru* made a great distinction between *Social services* and *Social welfare activities*. He always wanted to give top priority to the welfare of vulnerable social groups such as widowhood, women, children, disabled and victim of atrocities. The *Nehru* wanted *Social Welfare* to be inclusive of spiritual, cultural, political, economic, social and psychological wellbeing. Although *Nehru* could not term as Marxist, yet he talked about a classless society with equal opportunities full of selflessness, spiritual and cultural aspects and advocated a new world order based upon those principles. A Prime Minister having firmly believed that a welfare state must initiate every action aimed to facilitate social security to citizens. The socialist principles of *Nehru* could get reflected in his foreign and social issues as *Nehru* was appearing more influenced by '*Satyagrah*' of *Gandhi* and his ideas were never communist and well accorded by the world community (G., 2012). Nevertheless, *Nehru* was a modern view and he had realized that without considerable progress of science and technologies the country would not able to sustain the growth that is why he laid foundations of several educational, science and technology institutions and agencies in the country. Contrary to *Nehru* ideas, Dr. Manmohan Singh adopted different model. He promoted private,

corporate and talked about corporate social responsibilities. However, coming to office he kept silence over several key issues and remained never so connected with the people. How such shift occurred in the Congress party itself over the time-required study. Anyway, Dr. Manmohan Singh tenure was almost about to complete two successive terms involving almost ten years. Flagship programs like National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) and Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Program or MNREGA launched during his regime. The food security bill also introduced during his regime in the parliament. However, his second term became marred by corruption charges and unchecked inflation, which so suffocating for the people.

Lal Bahadur Shastri was also no less socialist as his slogan *Jai Jawan - Jai Kisan* was so close to people. Indira Gandhi started mission to eliminate poverty and her twenty formula programs was quite remarkable. The nationalization of banks could credit to her. Further Rajiv Gandhi hasn't just had a vision rather he also wanted to give his vision a shape. That's why he promoted *Punchayati Raj Institutions* and started *Jawahar Rojgar Yojna* to support the rural and folk societies in India. Narsingh Rao came to the office of the Prime Minister of India completed a full term amidst great political uncertainty. The National Democratic Alliance or NDA government under the leadership of Sri Atal Bihari Bajpayee could also so significant because of that indicated a comprehensively weakened Congress Party. Then NDA government initiated several developmental projects and planned some major plans such as a National River Connection program, Highways programs. He definitely succeeded in keeping people hopes alive. The *Sarva Shiksha Abiyan* launched during his regime and NRHM formulated.

The very tenures of several Prime Ministers Such as G.N. Nanda, Chaudhary Charan Singh, V.P Singh, Chandrasekhar, I.K. Gujral and Devegowda short lived yet they could no way ignore. In a democracy, a Prime Minister has to connect with people and how a Prime Minister usually do was a matter of individual attitudes. *Nehru*, *Indira*, *Rajiv* and even *Atal Bihari Bajpayee* so easily established rapport with the population that messed with different Prime Ministers, especially who came to office for limited periods and in a casual manner? The contribution of a Prime Minister towards Social Welfare required investigation and presentation according to great traditions and customs of academic research.

Research questions or hypothesis:

Considering the fact that capacity, role and functions of a Prime Minister so important for the Social Welfare the key research questions under this research would be to:

1. What are the respective contributions of different Prime Ministers towards *Social Welfare* in India?
2. What are the programs and launched during the tenure of different Prime Ministers?
3. What policies adopted by different Prime Ministers with respect to Social Welfare?
4. On what basis a Prime Minister could term as best Prime Minister for strengthening social welfare in India.

Methodology:

This was a qualitative form of research, inclusive of Literature Review, Case Studies and Interview Methods. The fieldwork involved with collection of literatures and information across the country. The tenure of each Prime Minister would be studied like a case study method.

Overview of literature:

The archives of proceedings of Lok Sabha and Rajyasabha could enable some extremely important source of information. Some other archives also could prove significant which would be exploited during the field work. There would be literatures available in the form of speeches, letters to Chief Ministers and deliberations at public meetings, committee meetings, and different national, international, and parliamentary forums by the respective Prime Ministers of India. Such literatures could constitute huge resources highly beneficial under this project. The Planning Commission constituted in India has some a great account of Plans and Prospects of Social Welfare in India (Planning Commission, 1951). Planning Commission has also some relevant accounts related to Social Welfare in India. In addition, the publication division of the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting has published speeches of different Prime Ministers (India, 1954). Further, some more notions of Nehru could find in the book of *Gopal Sarvpalli* titled *Jawaharlal Nehru: An Anthology* (Sarvpalli, 1980). In a book written by V.R. Bhattacharya titled “*Some aspects of social security measures in India*” one could find more relevant information (Bhattacharya, 1970). Book by S.P. Aiyar titled “*Perspective on the welfare state*” was another major literature which has certain views expressed about the welfare of people by an Indian state (Aiyar, 1979). Further books by D.P. Choudhary titled “*A Handbook of social welfare*” (Choudhary, 1966), “*Social Legislation in India*” by K.D. Gangrade (Gangrade, 1978), “*Social Welfare: Legend and Legacy*” by S.D. Gokhale (Gokhale, 1975), “*Planning and the Poor*” by B.S. Minhas (Minhas, 1974) and “*Social Welfare in India: Mahatma Gandhi's Contribution*” by AM Mazumdar (Mazumdar, 1964) would be some other major and relevant literatures.

Conceptual framework:

Social Welfare meaning applied differently in different countries, yet it could say that providing satisfying standards of life and health to raise the capacity for wellbeing of the society, family or individual and maintaining perfect harmony among them. (Sachdeva, 2010). Social Welfare arrangements must include a level of Social Security to all members in case of Unemployment, Poverty, Illness or Death. For this a government has to work for, providing Housing, Vocational training, Healthcare, and *Social Change*. The role of government must also ensure favorable *Social Change*.

There are distinct differentiations among the terms of *Social Welfare*, *Social Services/ Social Work* and *Philanthropy*. Many countries of the world considered Social Welfare as being synonymous to Social Services/ Work and Philanthropy, however, in India we could find that a *State* and its *governments* adopted *Social Welfare* as a policy of the government what could reflect in different programs in the field of education, health, housing, water & sanitation, nutrition, insurance and employment guarantee programs. In addition Indian governments further supported programs through voluntary or philanthropic organizations for the welfare of vulnerable groups such as Schedule castes, Schedule tribes, economically weaker sections, orphans, widows, unmarried mothers, elderly people, beggars, prostitutes, differently able people, impoverished and jobless (UN, 1970).

The well-being of the entire society could not be limited to living standard, however more related to quality of life and may include environmental issues, crime, drug abuse, availability of social services, and religious and cultural aspects. The concept of *Social Security* has been enshrined in Article 22 of the universal declaration of human rights. It

further stated that every member of society had the right to Social Security and entitled to realization, through national effort and international cooperation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State (UN, 1978). *Social Security* also referred to the action programs of government intended to promote the welfare of the population through assistance measures guaranteeing access to sufficient resources for food and shelter and to promote health and wellbeing for the population at large and potentially vulnerable segments such as children, elderly, sick and the unemployed (Wikipedia, 2013).

The term *Welfare*, *Social Welfare* and *Social Service* differed in definitions, scope, arrangements, policies and administration. The term *Social Welfare* has a different set of policies, programs and administration. It is involved with a government, whereas *Welfare* involved with the State and *Social Service* included nongovernmental, philanthropic or foreign agencies, whereas the role of government could be of a facilitator.

Most of the Prime Ministers in India acquired office amidst major turmoil for example Nehru became Prime Minister when colonial masters left the country in turmoil marred with communal violence and chaos, anarchy. He had the responsibility to correct the administration and laid the foundation for governance of India. He selected democracy, secularism and non-alignment as core foundations and welfare, socialism as core principles of the governance. After diminishing of Nehru, L.B. Shastri acquired office and was no less committed to socialism and democratic values. After Shastri's death in the year 1966, Indira Gandhi became the Prime Minister of India, however under her regime, Indian foreign policy came closer to the former USSR and moved away from USA. During the cold war period, India has to suffer despite India being committed to non-aligned. Amidst one of the major revolution led by Jayprakash Narayan, Indira Gandhi removed from office in the year 1977 however; she was able to make a comeback and again came to power in the year 1980. After her assignation in October 1984, the country was engulfed by the communal violence. Amidst that uncertainty, Rajiv Gandhi became the Prime Minister. Narsingh Rao became Prime Minister in the year 1991 because of sudden assignation of Rajiv Gandhi by LTTE guerrillas. The country witnessed tremendous social unrest in the name of *manadal* and *kamanadal* movement during 1990s. In 1998, Atal Bihari Bajpayee became the Prime Minister amidst great political uncertainties. Manmohan Singh dislodged Atal Bihari Bajpayee and defeated BJP iron man L. K. Advani to come to power in 2004 and 2009 respectively. The tenure of several other Prime Ministers was not so long yet they required appraisal with a certain point of views.

The issues investigated under this research may include social- economic conditions, demand, need and approach during the tenure of a Prime Minister. For these sake speeches of Prime Ministers, House Proceedings of *Rajyasabha* and *Lok Sabha*, Deliberations at different national-international forums would be considered. The policies adopted during the tenure of a prime minister and how that policy influenced and Social Insurance, Pension Schemes, Disability Insurance, Sickness and Unemployment insurances are some major issues, which would under the purview of this research.

Therefore, this research would investigate the core policies and programs of the government of India and how those policies and programs influenced by different Prime Ministers. How different Prime Ministers also motivated

different provincial governments to arrange policies and programs for *Social Welfare*.

Implications:

This paper would definitely have some tremendous policy implications. It could largely observe that very initiatives of social welfare and social security at the levels of respective societies being not so much supported by the government and in addition the response of government over several particular issued with respect to social welfare and social security has been so slow and deficient. In addition, they're more often suffering from delays and inadequacy. Due to privatization of Indian economy several resources mover in private hands, however, they failed to live with their promises of adequate social responsibilities. In addition, they tried to divert the attention of people from key issues with the means of irrational sports activities, TV programs, News channels and supporting fringe organizations. Political leaders becoming more concerned towards media channels, fringe organizations had definitely disconnected from actual people and never hearing their voices adequately.

Findings:

Starting from the first Prime Minister *J. L. Nehru* to the present *Narendra Damodar Das Modi*, some prime ministers have contributed significantly to the cause of social welfare one way or another.

If *Nehru* can be remembered for his contribution in the form of strengthening the model of a democratic welfare state and federalism, *Narendra Modi* can be remembered for good governance and administration.

Several acts including labour welfare legislations were passed during the *Nehru's* regime. However, he could be also remembered for a national shame of compromising national territories in *Kashmir* and North with *Pakistan* and *China* respectively. *Lal Bahadu Shastri*, though lived in an office for a short period, nevertheless he may be remembered for his notion and ideas of *Jai Jawan* and *Jai Kisan*. *Shastri* was succeeded by *Indira Gandhi*, who could be attributed for creating a new wave of reconnaissance among women. She truly contributed significantly to the feminine gender. Her son *Rajiv Gandhi* can be remembered for promoting a scientific thought among the youth of India. The period of 1991 and 2014 was quite significant for India as India adopted and started a journey towards liberalization, privatization, and globalization. *Atal Bihari Bajpayee* started a mega project for education, namely *Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan* and Rural Road Improvement schemes in addition to some nutrition and programs. One of his best achievements could be that he safeguarded the Indian economy, however, failed to avoid conflict in *Kargil* and terrorist attacks on Parliament, Red Fort, Civilian and Military Installations. His visit to *Lahore*, aimed at improving bilateral relations with *Pakistan* resulted in a great deception.

Prime Minister *Manmohan Singh* could be contributed for two mega schemes such as National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), and Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Abhiyan (MNREGA). However, his tenure of 2014- 2014 witnessed in several corruption charges, sharp currency devaluation, inflation. The provisions of 6th and 7th pay commission overburdened the public exchequer. There was a sharp rise in imports, whereas, exports declined. Rise

of labour cost in India created a situation Indian skilled workforce became idols and forced to remain jobless. This situation also promoted more and more imports.

Narendra Modi can be remembered for his contribution towards good governance and administration. He also became able to cut short, terrorists and Maoists activities. His programs of Housing, LPG Cylinders, Jan Dhan Yojna, Rural Electrification Program, National Sanitation Program, PM Adarsh Gram Yojna, One Rank and One Pension for Ex-Army Personnel was some major contribution. In addition, it has been known from a reliable sources that he is also working on a universal social security program. He also remained successful in maintaining a communal and social harmony in the country. He right now appearing to be a good mixture of politics, economy, and administration.

References:

- Aiyar, S. (1979). *Perspective on the Welfare State*. New Delhi: Ajmer Sachin Publications.
- Bhattacharya, V. (1970). *Some Aspects of Social Security Measures in India*. New Delhi: Metropolitan Book Company.
- Chittaranjan, C. (1973). *Nehru and Socialism*. New Delhi: Mainstream.
- Choudhary, D. P. (1966). *A Hand Book of Social Welfare*. Delhi: Atmaram & Sons.
- Commission, P. (1951). *First Five Year Plan*. New Delhi: Government of India.
- Commission, P. (1951). *Plans and Prospects of Social Welfare in India*. New Delhi: Government of India.
- G., K. V. (2012). *Jawahar Lal Nehru's Foreign Policies*. Solapur, Maharastra: CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH IN INDIA: VOL. I, ISSUE: I (ISSN 2231-2137).
- Gangrade, K. (1978). *Social Legislation in India*. Delhi: Concept Publishing House.
- Gokhale, S. (1975). *Social Welfare: Legend and Legacy*. Bombay: Popular Prakashan.
- India, G. O. (1954). *Jawahar Lal Nehru's Speeches*. New Delhi: Ministry of Information and Broadcasting.
- Mahashwetadevi. (1990). *Nehru's Dream of Socialism*. Kolkata: Mainstream.
- Mazumdar, A. (1964). *Social Welfare in India: Mahatma Gandhi's Contribution*. Bombay: Asia Publishing House.
- Minhas, B. (1974). *Planning and the Poor*. New Delhi: S. Chand & Co.
- Sachdeva, D. D. (2010). *Social Welfare Administration in India*. New Delhi: Kitab Mahal.
- Sarvapalli, G. (1980). *Jawaharlal Nehru: An Anthology*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Shiya. (2012). *Brief notes on Nehru and Democratic Socialism*. Delhi: Mainstream.
- UN. (1970). *Social Welfare Planning in the Context of National Development Plans*. New York: United Nations.
- UN. (1978). *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*. Retrieved May 01, 2013, from <http://www.un.org/cyberschoolbus/humanrights/resources/plain.asp>
- Walsh, R. J. (1940). *Towards Freedom: The Autography of Jawahar Lal Nehru*. New York: Cornwall Press, INC.
- Wikipedia. (2013, May). *Welfare: Social Welfare*. Retrieved May 01, 2013, from Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_welfare
